

A STUDY ON THE LENGTH EFFECT INFLUENCING THE MECHANICAL STRENGTH OF GLASS FIBRE FILAMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The manufacturing industry of reinforced materials has to deal with several influences to gain good results of their manufactured parts which may not result from the material itself. For example, during the continuous manufacturing Winding - Process different dry roving lengths at the feeding system of the machine can influence the process before the actual manufacturing. In addition to that a necessary load on the roving bundle must be supplied to gain good manufacturing results in the end. In actual winding processes it often appears that the preloaded fibre bundle fails to a lower strength than the given tensile strength out of the data sheet. The reason for this behaviour is a combination of free fibre length and in that case a change in the statistical distribution of the tensile strength and the necessary preload on the fibres. Tensile strength of glass fibres exhibits statistical Weibull type distribution and significant size dependence.

In the present work the strain rate dependency and also a possible length dependency was investigated. These analyses are based on the needs of the manufacturing industry for continuous manufacturing processes. As very import information the maximum strength of dry fibre filaments depending on the actual fibre length will be investigated. This is crucial for adjusting the feeding system of the reinforcements to the actual manufacturing machine.

For the first part in this work, a systematic analysis of glass fibre samples with different lengths influencing the mechanical strength of fibre bundles is introduced. As a next step glass fibres were tested with different gauge lengths. The length effect were analysed and based on that results different interpretations were made. Thereby, at first the strain rate dependency was analysed and based on that information a strain rate which presented a suitable manufacturing speed for continuous processes was chosen for the actual tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Starting its development as an aerospace material, fibre-reinforced and particle-reinforced composites have been increasingly used in other industries, for example automobiles, marine transport, buildings and civil infrastructure, sporting goods, medical equipment and prosthetic devices, etc. With the increased use of composite materials, there is a tremendous need to develop efficient manufacturing techniques, economical and effective repair techniques and methods to predict the short- and long-term behaviour of the composite materials and structures made of these materials under a variety of loading and environmental conditions. In addition to the aforementioned requirements, the construction and processing need to fulfill the highest requirements in the weight and mechanical properties [1].

Recently, the need for high-performance, low-weight structures has been growing and the demand for polymer matrix composites (PMCs) that have high specific strength and stiffness will continue to grow. Glass fibres are the most widely used reinforcement in PMCs. Approximately 90% of PMC products contain glass fibres; their popularity is mainly due to their low cost and high performance. Glass fibre-reinforced plastics (GFRPs) are used extensively to manufacture various products such as fishing rods, storage tanks, and marine structures. It has been reported that glass fibres show unique characteristics not observed in carbon fibres. The strength of glass fibres increases with increasing strain rate, and increases with decreasing temperature or humidity, although glass is a brittle material [2].

Glass fibres and glass-reinforced plastics appear to behave as brittle materials. One of the most characteristic traits of brittle materials is the effect of structural size on the fracture strength. To explain these effects, Griffith introduced the concept that glass contains pre-existing flaws, so that the fracture process is one of crack propagation rather than crack initiation. Weibull extended this concept by reasoning that the flaws are randomly distributed throughout the body and are of random severity. The "weakest-link" approach was adopted as a criterion of failure or a brittle material fails when the stress at any one flaw becomes larger than the ability of the surrounding material to resist the local stresses. Applying the statistical laws of probability, Weibull assumed a reasonable distribution function and derived the expression [3, 4].

Mechanical strength of glass fibres has puzzled scientific researchers for a long time, and still today the origin of high strength of glass fibres is actively discussed around the world. Glass is one of the oldest known man-made materials. The practical strength of glass, however, has always been a limiting and puzzling factor. It is known that, the measurable strength of glass fibres is much larger than that of bulk glasses of similar chemical composition. An understanding of how and why the glass breaks is crucial in both improving existing applications of glasses and in achieving new functionalities and in finding new application of glasses [5].

2 BACKGROUND

2.1. Tensile strength

Glass is one of the oldest known man-made materials; the practical strength of glass, however, has always been a limiting and puzzling factor. Still today the mechanical properties of glass fibres are twofold a) a special quality is the high strength b) the brittle fracture is limiting its application. An understanding of the structure of glass in relation to how and why it breaks is crucial in both improving existing applications of glasses and in new functionalities and application of all kinds of glasses, not only fibre glass.

Strength of a material is basically the resistance to break. When glass breaks it happens catastrophically – in brittle failure. There are two phenomena that dominate brittle failure; it is fast fracture and fatigue degradation. The failure mechanism is believed to be identical, but the time to failure is different [6]. As mentioned in the previous section in glass the resistance to break is controlled by the possibility of a fracture to initiate and to grow; hence the origin and the intrinsic fracture toughness. Primary focus of the present study is the fast fracture. The theoretical strength is directly related to the stress it requires to break the chemical bonds between two adjacent atoms in the

glass structure. This means that the inter-atomic spacing is proportional to the inverse of the theoretical strength. During fracturing two new surfaces are produced as the chemical bonds are broken (increasing the surface area). Orowan approximated the theoretical strength as the work per surface area supplied to produce fracture. The Orowan equation of theoretical strength, σ :

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\gamma_s \frac{E}{a}} \quad (1)$$

where γ_s = surface energy (fracture energy per surface unit), E = elastic modulus, a = intraatomic distance [6].

Hence the strength depends on the elastic modulus, the surface energy and the glass structure. In measuring the strength the actual experimental values of strength are only around 1/100 to 1/1000 of the theoretical strength. In the search of an explanation to why measured strength of glass is considerable lower than calculation of the strength required to break the chemical bonds, much research has already in the early days focused on the material surfaces. The earliest quantitative work on strength in glasses was performed in 1920 by Griffith, who used glass as a model material to investigate the influence of surfaces on material strength from an engineering point of view [3]. Based on the stress concentration analysis [7] Griffith hypothesized that the existence of cracks on the glass surfaces will lower the apparent strength of the material because stress concentration is experienced at the cracks as an external load is applied. The Griffith fracture theory is based on the statistical principle of minimum potential energy. In the case of crack growth the only contribution to energy changes result from the new fracture surfaces and converts strain energy of the material into fracture energy. Hence, the fracture will grow when it is energetically favourable. By his equation Griffith related the external load to the length of a pre-existing crack within the glass. The Griffith equation is given in E.q. 2 where E is the elastic modulus and γ is the surface energy and c the length of the pre-existing crack (also called the Griffith flaw) [3]:

$$\sigma_f = \left(\frac{2E\gamma}{\pi c} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

Freshly drawn glass monofilaments can lose strength in many ways. Exposure to certain atmospheres and mechanical handling are the principal means by which strength is lost. Both of these means indicate strongly that the loss of strength is related to events occurring on the surface. This contention is supported by observations [8] from decoration techniques that typical flaw densities on glass fibres are 10^2 to 10^3 per cm^2 or flaws are 0.3 to 3 cm apart on fibres of 40×10^{-5} inch diameter. Accordingly, the approach taken in this work has been to assume that the statistical analysis should be on the basis of area rather than the more general volume basis developed earlier from the Kies and Weibull analyses. In the case of constant diameter fibres, a further generalization has been made in terms of length, L , rather than area. [9]

2.2. Strain rate

Hayakawa et al. [10] confirmed that the strength of E-glass fibres doubled when the temperature was decreased from room temperature to cryogenic temperature (-196°C). Arao et al. [11] found that the strength of glass fibres in a resin increased by approximately 33 % through the removal of moisture around the fibre surface. The effects of strain rate on the strength of glass fibres have been investigated by many researchers. An increase in the strength, fracture strain, and the impact strength of the GFRP with increasing strain rate has been confirmed by other literatures [12–15].

Although it has been verified that glass fibres have excellent impact properties, the mechanism for the strain-rate dependence of the fibre strength has not yet been clarified.

The strain-rate dependence for the strength of glass fibre may be due to the following factors:

- A temperature rise during the test
- Modification of the molecular structure
- The effect of thermal residual stress in glass fibres
- The effect of a stress wave
- The propagation of surface flaws during the test. Because the strain-rate dependence in carbon fibres is extremely small, the strain rate dependence in glass fibres may be caused by the unique characteristic of glass.

3 TEST SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TESTING

For all test standard S-Glass roving with 4800 tex were taken. To ensure equal strain onto the roving the specimens have to be prepared before inserting them into the tensile testing rig. This is done by using two-component epoxy glue and roughened aluminium plates for a better application of force into the roving sample. To make sure that all single filaments are glued together low viscosity glue was used. To ensure that the applied test forces will be held by the epoxy matrix a special treatment was applied. The roving end is glued in between 2 aluminium plates with a diameter of 20 mm x 10 mm. During the bounding process a pressure of 1.5 bar for 100 seconds and a temperature of 100 °C were applied. Due to that process a bounding force between the two aluminium plates and the roving bundle in between of 2500 N/cm² was reached. The significant testing length between the plates was varied: 50 mm, 150 mm, 300 mm, 500 mm, 800 mm, 1000 mm and 1200 mm.

Figure 1: Sample preparation for tensile test with variable sample length.

All tests were performed on one testing rig:

- Tensile testing rig from company Zwick (Zwick / Roell Z250)
- Mechanical clamping device (clamping area of 20 mm x 10 mm)
- Testing rig was strain rate controlled (in an area of $5 \cdot 10^{-5} - 10 \text{ s}^{-1}$)
- Measurements were stopped after the measured force seceded under 10 % off the ultimate tensile strength

Figure 2: Zwick Testing rig and testing sample clamping.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Strain rate dependency

It was verified that the strength of glass fibre depends on the strain rate due to the slow crack growth of glass. This result was also shown for the dry glass roving tests in this work.

The results of the present analysis of the strain rate dependency were the basic analysis to get an intention of the strain rate influencing a continuous composite manufacturing process under real circumstances e.g. processing speed. There is a great deal of data available for the dynamic strength of GFRP, however, there are only a few reports about the dynamic properties of dry glass fibres. Therefore, tensile tests of fibre bundles were conducted at various strain rates to determine the maximum tensile strength. For fibre bundle tests, friction between each fibre can have significant influence on the strength results. The friction of fibre degrades the strength of fibre bundle. However, it is difficult to increase strain rate for long gauge length in the dynamic loading test. The load and displacement of the crosshead were monitored during the test. The strain rate was within the range $5 \cdot 10^{-5} - 10 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 3 shows the maximum tensile strength of glass fibre bundle at quasi-static and high strain rate. Overall tests the standard deviation was roundabout 20 – 25 %. It is concerned that the tab

constriction and the clamping inaccuracy affects test results. The specimens were always prepared by using same tab and same procedure from always the same operating researcher to minimize the deviation as much as possible. It was found the fibre fractured between gauge regions, not at the edge of the tabs. The strength of fibre bundle could be successfully obtained by this experiment. The result, shown in Fig. 3, is an example for the strain rate dependency at one gauge length ($l = 150$ mm). It appears that the strength of the glass fibre increased at high strain rate and consequently the failure strain increases drastically with the strain rate. This tendency corresponds with the few results for already tested dry fibre in the literature and is also congruent with strain rate test for glass fibre composite parts.

Figure 3: Strain rate dependency for testing length $l = 150$ mm.

4.2. Length dependency

Due to the results of the strain rate tests the length dependency tests were performed under constant strain rate conditions. Therefore the strain rate was set to $6 \cdot 10^{-3} s^{-1}$ for all different tested gauge lengths. After analysing the results a standard deviation of at max 10 – 15 % was found and this standard deviation is comparable with other dry fibre test.

Figure 4 shows that the strength versus length plot leaves a huge area of interpretation for E-glass over the range of lengths. Included in these figures are the measures data from 50 mm up to 1200 mm free sample length. All of these results and there possible interpretation indicate that due to shorter lengths the maximum possible applied strength raises to higher values. Unfortunately, the test methods for higher lengths were not possible during the study because of the limitation of the measurement equipment.

Figure 4: Length dependency a various interpretation possibilities.

As one of the best interpretations for the length behaviour the asymptotic fit has proven to be the best choice to reproduce the length dependency. This fact leads to the prediction that after a certain free sample length no further decrease of the maximum tensile strength depending on raising test lengths will happen. In this study this effect started (shown in Figure 4, blue line) to occur at roundabout 1000 mm free sample length. As one explanation for the tensile strength plateau the interactions between the dry fibres may be possible. For example single filaments failed at lower strength values are wrapping around their adjoining fibres and in combination with based on that fact appearing friction the initial load can be diverted to the rest of the intact single fibres. Based on that the actual dry testing bundles act in a kind of way like fibre composite and if there are enough fibres splitting up the initial load to more than one single fibre the effect of a tensile strength plateau can be described. To prove this theory more tests will be necessary.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, the tensile strength of glass fibres were studied and based on that results the strain rate on further on a possible length dependency including a theory to explain the analysed results were given. Dry S-Glass fibres with 4k single filaments were main objects of this study. The focus of the study was placed on the dependence of the tensile strength with the needs and wishes of continuous manufacturing processes kept in mind.

The strain rate dependency for dry fibre glass fibre bundles showed the same behaviour as for example glass fibre reinforced composite testing parts. The results showed that the maximum tensile strength was increased with higher strain rates.

For shorter free sample lengths the length dependency test had shown that the tensile strength increased. As another interesting effect this test came to the result that there was a possible tensile strength plateau reached for higher testing lengths. This could be explained by the interaction of failed single filaments during the tests with their adjoining fibres through possible higher friction. To gain more information about this effect further test will be necessary.

Over all tests it could be said that the influence of the operating persons, especially for the testing sample preparation, was of significant importance. Based on that knowledge the sample preparation was handled very carefully leading to a good standard deviation of a maximum of 25 % for the strain rate tests and an even lower standard deviation of less than 15 % for the length dependency test.

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